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A Case for Case Instruction of Engineering Ethics

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INTRODUCTION

Recently, the use of case studies for teaching engineering ethics attracted criticism pointing to its inadequacy in capturing the complexity of the profession [19], [5]. Our paper examines case instruction of engineering ethics, arguing that the microethical use of this teaching method does not fully capture the metaphysical and epistemological dimension of engineering. We proceed by looking in the first section at the beginnings of case instruction, highlighting its main characteristics and benefits according to empirical research. We then zoom in on the use of case studies for engineering ethics instruction, presenting four deficiencies that fail to fully materialize the strengths of the method. We claim that these deficiencies are rooted in a microethical approach to engineering ethics education, which leads to a dilution of the major features of case pedagogy.

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1 CASE STUDY PEDAGOGY: CHARACTERISTICS AND BENEFITS

Case studies were first used as a teaching method in law and business, their history tracing back to the law professor and dean of Harvard Law School Christopher Langdell, who first taught a case study in 1870. The cases designed by Langdell were inspired by real sources and were meant to encourage students' independent thinking, thus moving away from the lecture and recitation format focused on presenting information and then asking students to memorize it. Harvard Business School adopted the method almost 100 years ago, in 1920, under the leadership of Wallace Brett Donham, himself a law graduate. With Donham as dean, the school developed approximately 18000 cases during a 27 year span.

How case studies are conceptualized and taught varies between disciplines. The dialogical format of case studies became the mark of legal education [25], while in the medical field case studies developed as problem based learning, with students receiving patient records based on which they had to formulate diagnostic hypotheses or propose treatment protocols [13]. Although the case study method is not the same as problem based learning, both approaches are inductive in nature, drawing inferences from particular instances and empirical observations. The inductive format proved suitable in addressing ill-structured problems like the ones typically arising in law, business and medicine, such that case centered pedagogy grew to become a widespread teaching method in these fields [13].

[18] defines ill-structured problems as allowing conceptualization of multiple - sometimes opposing - solutions, which means there is "no explicit means for determining appropriate action" [16, p. 69]. In the absence of generalizable principles and a directive theory, contextual factors play a significant role that can both shape and constrain action. Such problems thus contain "uncertainty about which concepts, rules, and principles are necessary for the solution or how they are organized" [23, p.8], and so evade deductive approaches that rely on inferences from general theories towards an anticipated solution which is logically sound. Besides their inductive format, other important characteristics of case studies are:

- verisimilitude

Case studies are meant to closely reflect features of a profession [13]. They are expected to contain authentic problems an engineer might encounter [27]. As such, case studies "illustrate the art of engineering and help students cultivate judgment and an appreciation of what is involved in that attribute" [31, p.56]. Thus, they manage to capture the "background and complexities actually encountered by an engineer" [17].

- extensive scope

[1, p. 234] notes that a case study is "more general in its framework and purpose than a normal engineering problem, including the interaction of engineering and non-engineering topics." As opposed to typical well-structured problems employed in engineering pedagogy that have a strong or exclusive mathematical component, case studies include additional aspects that are part of engineering practice. Besides technical information, they also rely on contextual information [24]. [11, p.413] remarks that case studies consider "not only quantitative relations amenable to computations, but other factors such as the interactions of people, the malevolence of inanimate objects, and the pressures of time and resources under which engineers work".

-context driven

Given their extended scope and realistic character, case studies have a significant contextual component [7]. This can include information about the various stakeholders involved in the design and decision process of an engineering project, socio political and economic attributes of the environment in which the project is set, organizational details, a.o. Context gains a crucial importance that cannot be neglected, as it can shape or restrain individual agency. Different contextual information can lead to different strategies for tackling the scenario, allowing even the possibility that none of these strategies is entirely satisfactory.

- tolerate and even cultivate ambiguity and complexity

This means there is no predetermined strategy or theory that can be applied to reach a desired solution, as well as no predetermined ideal outcome. Case studies contain a wide range of contextual information, often ambiguous, leading to a lack of clarity whether one or another specification or constraint should weigh in when deciding on a strategy, or how each factor can affect the outcome. Case studies allow to be formulated as to incorporate “the complexities and ambiguities of real-world ethical problems in an effective and memorable way” [28, p.11].

-multidimensional perspective

As such, case studies are envisioned to tradeoff certainty for nuances. The lack of a definite absolute solution or a predetermined solution path means that a problem can be represented in various ways, and the perspectives of multiple subjects influence the design and decision making process. [16, p.81] remarks that “ill-structured problems possess multiple solutions because there are multiple representations of the problem. The problem solver’s perceptions of problem constraints are the primary factors that determine which alternative is selected.” Thus, case studies can make students aware of others’ viewpoints and how to take them into account. Unlike textbook problems that assume a single objective viewpoint, in the formulation of case studies various stances are voiced. Such that “in the presentation of a case study, every attempt is made to provide an unbiased multidimensional perspective”[24, p.54].

-allow interactions

The inclusion of different perspectives in the problem description means that unlike textbook problems, case studies are dynamic. The solution emerges out of a wide array of factors and subjectivities that interact in the design and decision making process of an engineering project. The scenarios presented by case studies can thus be enacted by participants to simulate such interactions [21].

The success of case studies in addressing complex and ill-structured problems in law and business prompted their adoption in 1950s also in engineering. As [26] point out, the traditional methods employed in engineering instruction are deductive, focused on providing principles for deriving mathematical models and showing their application. Research focused on case instruction highlighted several benefits for engineering education. [34] conducted a survey among 101 science faculty members in US and Canada, which revealed that the use of case studies improved students’ critical-thinking skills, the ability to make connections across multiple content areas and the understanding of concepts. Instructors also considered that case studies helped students to better view an issue from multiple perspectives.

2 CASE STUDIES IN THE TEACHING OF ENGINEERING ETHICS

In regards to the use of case studies in teaching engineering ethics, there is little or no empirical evidence proving its effectiveness compared to other teaching methods [35]. In other fields such as medical education, case studies were shown to significantly increase students' awareness of ethical issues compared to students who were not exposed to this teaching method [20]. Despite no proven benefits, case study pedagogy is nevertheless the prevalent method employed in teaching ethics in engineering colleges in U.S. [4].

There are two major frames for teaching engineering ethics according to [15, p. 373]: a microethical approach focused on ethical dilemmas faced by individual engineers, and a macroethical approach concerned with "the collective responsibilities of the profession and societal decision making about technology." The goal of the first is refining moral reasoning or developing moral character. While the later, by treating engineers as members of social, political or organizational structures, is envisioned to enable correcting those structures "that may need to be changed if engineering and technology are to contribute to human welfare" [5, p. 226].

We argue that microethical case instruction is weak on both metaphysical and epistemological grounds. From a metaphysical perspective, the microethical use of case study in the teaching of engineering ethics fails to fully capture features of the engineering profession related to the nature of (i) the artefacts produced [3], [33], (ii) engineering practice [2], [29]) and (iii) the professional environment [6], [8]. While the epistemological deficits of the microethical use of case studies, focused on clear cut dilemmas and situations of crisis, rest on the assumption that (iv) engineering knowledge is fully explicit and readily available by consulting codes and theory, neglecting its strong tacit and practice based character [30], [32].

2.1 Metaphysical deficits of microethical case instruction

There are three ways in which the microethical use of case studies in engineering ethics fails to capture the metaphysical characteristics of the engineering profession:

(i) A first objection from a metaphysical perspective is that microethical approaches to case studies seem to elude the nature of engineering artefacts. These are not mere products whose creation is restricted to the application of scientific principles, but they also comprise a certain social dynamic or can have political effects [33]. As [33] has argued, a bridge can display one's view about race or social class, inasmuch as it displays technological expertise, as the example of the bridges in Long Island designed by Moses shows. [3, p. 10] further elaborates on how technical artifacts are important in the constitution of power. What seems now an unproblematic everyday engineering artefact, the fluorescent lamp, is in fact the outcome of "a complex economic power play in which General Electric, the electric utilities, the U.S. government, and consumers all played roles. Conversely, the power map of the electric manufacturing scene in the United States was substantially modified by the introduction of the new lamp." By being formulated according to a binary scenario focused on disaster and prevention, case studies tend to neglect the political or social beliefs that govern the creation of engineering artefacts and the manner in which technology mediates human activity.

(ii) Second, as [2, p. 15] points out, the practice of engineering is not solely an application of technical skills, but "a social process involving interaction between the

design team, the client and others". Microethical case studies present an individualistic perspective that asks an agent to take a decision – postpone the Challenger launch, design weapons of mass destruction - neglecting what [9] call "the social arrangements for making decisions". There are different subjectivities involved in engineering practice, each with their own values, backgrounds and goals, which come to shape the solution chosen, the artefact created or even the meaning of the values in use. [29] shows how incremental change over time in what was considered acceptable risk by the organizational culture of NASA led to a "normalization of deviance," which later contributed to the explosion of the Challenger shuttle. What happened was that the meaning and range of what was deemed "safe" was altered through the continual interaction of multiple subjects.

(iii) Third, microethical case instruction rests on the assumption that moral values are independent and objective, rather than embedded within a social or political context, institutional practice or corporate culture. If we consider that making a moral choice in engineering means pursuing values such as social responsibility, safety and sustainability, and these values exist independently, we are assuming full agency to pursue them on the part of the individual. In this case, the engineer is regarded as having agency regardless of the characteristics of the structure she is part of. Cases describing moral dilemmas are seen to allow for a win-win outcome, which given the objective nature of moral values, can be solved through appeal to professional codes or ethical theories [6]. In practice however, even if the engineer successfully identifies a course of action, she might still be unable to act upon her moral beliefs given the contextual constraints encountered [8].

2.2 Epistemological deficits of microethical case instruction

The dominant underlying assumption of microethical case instruction about what type of knowledge engineers use in their day to day practice is divergent with the way in which engineers conduct their practice. Case studies presenting clear cut dilemmas and situations of crisis that can be solved through appeal to professional codes or moral theories assume that engineering knowledge is fully explicit and readily available by consulting theoretical provisions. [32] identifies six types of knowledge an engineer uses in her work, one of them being "practical considerations" represented by "information learnt mostly on the job and often possessed unconsciously, rather than in codified form." [14] also points out that according to interviews conducted with engineers, much of their expertise was based on tacit knowledge. While a study conducted by [12, p. 209] revealed that two-thirds of the knowledge structural engineers employ is practice generated, meaning it is "context specific" and "constructed in the course of everyday activities", with only a third representing historically established knowledge, retrieved from "design manuals, building codes [...] and the bulk of what they learned in university courses."

This sort of tacit knowledge, argue [30, p. 64], "is often essential when it comes to deciding what risks to take or uncertainties to accept instead of carrying out further tests or developing more accurate models." According to [14], the tacit character of engineering expertise had a significant contribution to the Challenger disaster, as Boisjoly was unable to articulate his tacit knowledge during a final meeting where it was "particularly hard to discuss tacit knowledge and experience-based intuitions." Practical as well as ethical judgements are made by appeal to tacit knowledge. This is due both to the rapid pace and pressure under which engineering work is carried,

and to the frequent lack of theories in tune with the continuous technological advancements in contemporary society that could recommend a line of action over the other, note [30]. The reality of engineering practice is often ahead of prescriptions immortalized in codes or regulations that one can appeal to or consult, and in their absence, an engineer relies on her expertise gained through years of practice.

By presenting black and white scenarios which take place in situations of crisis, based on concrete and certain data, case studies end up resembling well-structured textbook problems. Case studies were developed as an alternative to deductive mathematical exercise, with a clear cut answer and a predetermined reasoning procedure leading up to it. In microethical instruction, the ill-structured function of case study pedagogy dillutes into a well-structured approach to situations an engineering student might face as a professional.

These four metaphysical and epistemic deficiencies of the use of microethical case studies overlap with a dilution of important features of case pedagogy, purporting to their verisimilitude, multidimensional perspective, rich context, interactivity, ambiguity, implicitness and inductive character. A microethical approach leads to case studies neglecting their ill-structured function and the characteristics of the method. Thus, in order to render the metaphysical and epistemological dimension of the engineering profession, case studies used in the teaching of engineering ethics need to make students aware that: (i) the artefacts created incorporate **also** social and political values, (ii) the decision and design process of creating an artefact is **also** a social process, (iii) even if identifying the moral thing to do is a necessary first step for being a socially responsible engineer, acting upon it depends on wider structural factors, (iv) engineering practice often includes ambiguous problems that do not lead to an ideal solution. Macroethical approaches to case studies based on scenarios that integrate roleplay [22], rich contexts portraying institutional dynamics, governmental measures and policies ([10], [14]) as well as ambiguous data could better incorporate the major characteristics of case based instruction.

CONCLUSION

There is a rich potential for case studies to help enhance students' professional and ethical responsibility or the ability to understand engineering solutions in a global and societal context [26], but there is no consensus about the most effective means of developing and employing this method of instruction in engineering ethics courses. Our contribution aims to argue that a microethical approach to case studies is nevertheless unsuitable for teaching engineering ethics, as it does not capture the characteristics that made this method successful in other disciplines such as law, business or medicine. A microethical approach to case studies leads to four significant metaphysical and epistemological deficiencies in rendering the complexity of the engineering profession, which are linked to an application of case instruction that neglects the major characteristics of the method.

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